

CHARACTERISTICS AND NECESSITY OF TEACHER’S PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS

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Abstract:

Teachers come across a lot of problems during their professional careers. For that reason, they have to know the ways how to solve the problems. In this article, the notion of problem-solving in language teaching is discussed in details. The importance of understanding problem-solving by future language teachers is further developed.

Key words :

Problem-solving, teacher’s development, skill, competence, management, lesson, teacher.

Characteristics and Necessity of Teacher’s Problem-Solving Skills

Today, English is used as a global language, so the role of a FL teacher has changed since the demands and expectations of society and government grew. Hence, preparing English teachers who are ready to solve any problem in order to teach student as proficient users is a very essential issue, that is why one of the competences of FL teachers is problem-solving skill. Let us look at the

necessity to understand teachers' problem solving activity in the classroom. It is a process of closing the gap between what is and what is desired or problem solving is a systematic process of using creative thinking to identify or define a problem, create ideas, and implement the idea or ideas to solve classroom management problem. Thus, by acquiring creative problem solving skills teachers can also develop their classroom management ability. According to research the complexity of the teaching profession is reflected by the elements or components as differentiation of pre-while- and post-active phases of the teaching process (planning, acting, evaluating), the multidimensional setting of the interactive phase (classroom situations), and the multiple level (society, school, classroom, student) of the teaching task. All these elements are contiguous to solving some problems that appear before a teacher. Problem-solving including decision-making is the key characteristic in the teaching process and it can be viewed as consisting of practical problems, requiring deliberation and action for their solution. Moreover “Teachers must be prepared to handle unanticipated situations, to adapt current knowledge to deal with new problems, to learn radically new things in short, to deal constructively with change” (Silverman, Welty & Lyon, 1990, p 95).

Teachers apply problem-solving skills not only in interaction and classroom management but also when they evaluate selection and planning materials, as well as the achieved results of the lessons. So, the whole pedagogical process, starting with planning and concluding with self- evaluation, is seen as analysing, acting, reflecting, making decisions and solving problems. Consequently each component of the teachers activity is pervaded by problem solving activity, in particular, requiring a careful analysis of each situation, choice of objectives, development and monitoring of suitable learning opportunities, evaluation of their impact on students' achievement, responsiveness to students' learning needs and a personal or collective reflection on the whole educational process. Mastering problem-solving skills depends on, first the personal factors and experience. Problem-solving skills can be the link between knowledge and action, declarative and procedural

knowledge; therefore it has an important knowledge transfer role, too. It includes divergent (creative or lateral) and convergent (critical) thinking processes, as well as systems thinking (Isaksen, Dorval & Treffinger, 2011). Besides “Professionals can frame and reframe a problem as they work on it, testing out their interpretations and solutions, combining both reflection and action” (Calderhead J, 1989, p 44). Problem-solving for teachers is the pedagogical strategy that refer to solve all problems. The obtained language and instructional knowledge and skills make up a creative problem-solving capacity which can be used by teachers at working solution to the particular problem in hand. To further explore the importance and effectiveness of developing students’ problem-solving skills an observation was conducted. I observed the lectures and seminars of the course of “Methodology of ELT” conducted at the 3rd course. After that I have conducted needs analysis with the third-year students in Uzbekistan State World Languages University via questionnaire to identify whether the course provides a good opportunity for developing problem-solving skills. Total number of students involved was 16. The tests for the third-year students to check their abilities and needs in problem-solving which came across in the classroom were conducted.

According to the results, only 37, 5% of the students are satisfied with the content of the course, however 62, 5% of students do not think that course syllabus can develop problem-solving skills of future teachers. On the other hand, 100% of students answered positively on the question about suitability of the course for Future English teachers. Those controversial results prove that the designed course is aimed at learners’ needs, but lacks teaching materials which ensure developing problem-solving skills of future English teachers. The majority of students, that is 56, 2%, think that they would have difficulties on generating multiple solutions for a problem, however others disagreed with this statement and think that they can look at from various perspectives. 93, 7% that is majority, of participants are not satisfied with their mini-lessons and think that they could not find solutions for encountered problems. Moreover, 87, 5% of participants think that it would be good if the course covers models for solving problems. That means that the teachers have to revise their teaching

materials so that they will take into account developing learners' abilities on understanding and solving classroom problems. The results on the expansion of small problems related to pupils' perception and production are equal which proves that there is a need to give clear understanding and awareness of the causes and consequences of problems so that students feel responsibility while determining and solving the problems. According to 43, 7% of participants, there is a need to learn the steps of problem-solving process as these participants are tend to stop the process the implementation step. Based on the results of the experiment the conclusion can be made that the third-year students are quite satisfied with the organization of the course, however do not think that the course develop problem-solving skills of them. There is suitability of the course curriculum for their needs but the designed course lacks teaching materials, ways or models as well as logic and coherence, which ensure developing problem-solving skills. Moreover, there is a slight need to learn the steps of problem-solving process. As a conclusion, on the basis of mentioned above, it can be said that it is vital to take into account that problem solving skill is not a special competence of the FL teachers, it has interrelation with their language proficiency and cross-curricular competences. For that reason, it should be one of the necessary skills teachers need to possess in order be able to respond all the difficulties they face on every step of their professional activity.

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